

The Action of Light on Concentrated Aqueous Solution of Ammonium Thiocyanate.

By

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Marshall Homes has recently investigated (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 1690) the cause of the red colouration which is developed when a concentrated aqueous solution of ammonium thiocyanate is exposed to sun-light and which slowly disappears on keeping the coloured solution in the dark. This phenomenon was originally described by Liesegang (*Edor's Jahrb. Photographic*, 1894, 49).

On the strength of a rather small amount of experimental work, Holmes (*loc. cit.*) put forward the view that ammonium thiocyanate is decomposed into NH_4CN and sulphur according to the equation,

and that the insoluble sulphur thus obtained forms larger aggregates of submicroscopic sizes which are responsible for the pink colour. These sub-microns slowly unite to form bigger particles and thus give rise to the small amount of precipitate which is obtained after long exposure.

The account of Marshall Holmes' researches reached the hands of the authors when they were already engaged on photochemical studies of a similar nature and it was considered desirable to study the phenomenon more fully as the equation of the reaction as given by Holmes did not seem to indicate the exact state of affairs. Since the colour of the solution completely disappears in the dark and can be produced again and again in the light, the problem appeared to be analogous to the reversible transformation of anthracene into dianthracene, the only completely reversible reaction fully described in literature and it thus presented another interesting aspect of study.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Since there is always the possibility that the iron in the glass vessels may be responsible for the colour so produced, the following critical experiments were tried to get decisive information on this point:—

(1) Instead of glass, quartz vessels were employed.

(2) To solutions of ammonium thiocyanate of varying concentrations (7·95N, 7·16N, 6·44N, 5·8N, 5·22N, 4·7N) very dilute ferric perchloride solutions acidified with HCl were added in amounts which just failed to produce the pink colour. The vessels were then exposed to sun-light. A control experiment with ammonium thiocyanate alone was also started at the same time. It was noticed that the colouration could be produced in quartz vessels quite as easily as in a glass vessel and the solutions described under (2) did not develop more colour than the control solutions nor was the action any quicker and hence the possibility that the reaction between the iron salt and the ammonium thiocyanate to produce the ferric thiocyanate may be catalysed was ruled out. The reaction appeared to be independent of the iron ions and quite distinct from the well-known action of ferric salts with ammonium thiocyanate.

Effects of Varying the Concentration of Ammonium Thiocyanate.

Solutions of varying concentrations were placed in the sun. The concentrations tried were, 9N, 8·1N, 7·29N, 6·56N, 5·9N, 5·31N and 4·78N. The colour was deepest in the strongest solution.

After about 5 hours' exposure a precipitate began to appear in 5·31N. When this precipitate begins to form, the colour gets visibly paler, a tinge of yellow mixing with the red colour of the solution. The precipitate appeared next in 5·9N and 4·78N and then in order of strength, being last to appear in the strongest solution.

The precipitate was most copious in 5·31N solution and least in the strongest solution. The order of the amount of precipitate was approximately 5·31N > 5·9N > 4·78N > 5·56N > 7·29N > 8·1N > 9N. It was found that solutions below 3·5N did not give any colouration.

But this depends on the kind of light. On exposure to the December sun in the evening, even a solution of 4.5N did not get visibly coloured even after an exposure of half an hour.

Effect of the Intensity and Wave-length of Light on the Reaction.

In sunlight the pink colouration is developed in one minute, although in a very concentrated solution a faint pink can be discovered even after an exposure of ten seconds to the October sun. The precipitate takes from five to six hours to appear. The quartz mercury vapour lamp and the light of iron arc produced a distinct pink in about 2 minutes. The carbon arc, on the other hand, has a very feeble effect, even two hours' exposure to it being hardly equal to two minutes' exposure to the sun.

The colour goes on deepening with the length of exposure. Thus four days' exposure to the sun produced a deep red colouration.

In order to find out which particular wave-lengths were most effective, a card-board box with seven compartments was made. Each compartment had for it a window cut out from the Wratten monochromatic light filters. Solutions of the same strength (8N) were placed behind each filter, and the box was closed so that light from no place except through the light-filter could fall on the various solutions. The box was then lit up in sunlight for 6 hours. Violet light was found to be most effective. Blue light produced a very faint colour, no other compartment showed the slightest effect. The same results were obtained when the exposure had been extended to three days. From the experiments on the iron and carbon arcs, it is clear that ultra-violet light is most effective, and that the effective region extends from blue to the ultra-violet.

Effect of Storage.—A solution (8N) which had been kept in the dark for 2 weeks gave a pink colour immediately on exposure to the sun, there being no difference from a freshly prepared solution of the same strength. Another solution of strength 9N which had been kept in the dark for more than a month also showed no difference in its behaviour from a freshly prepared one. This is opposed to the observation of Holmes who found that a solution which has been stored for sometime did not get coloured on exposure.

Effect of Moisture.—The dry crystals did not undergo any change on insolation. When placed in open air, however, they

absorbed moisture, being hygroscopic. The concentrated solution thus formed at the surface became pink on exposure to the sun.

Action of Solvents.—Carbon disulphide and benzene when shaken up with the coloured solution of NH_4CNS dissolved it to a certain extent, without getting coloured themselves. Ether was coloured pink and retained this colour in the dark.

Effects of Heating.—On heating a coloured solution of NH_4CNS , the colour was discharged, and ammonia was given off. The loss of colour was synchronous with the active evolution of ammonia. On exposing such a solution again, it developed a colour, which disappeared on heating. The effect could be repeated any number of times. An uncoloured solution of NH_4CNS also gave off ammonia on heating.

Acidity of Solution.—The unexposed as well as the exposed and coloured solutions were found to be acidic. The salt is hydrolysed in solution producing HCNS which is a strong acid.

Action of Various Substances.—(i) On dilution beyond 3.5N, the colour disappeared.

(ii) The addition of alkalis, e.g., KOH , NH_4OH in such amount as to make the NH_4CNS solution alkaline, discharged the colour. Such a solution on exposure to the sun developed no colour. KCN , as Holmes found, also produced the same effect, but this is due to the hydrolysis of KCN in solution and the production of KOH .

(iii) On the addition of acids the colour developed more rapidly. On the addition of dilute H_2SO_4 to a freshly prepared solution, a pink colour appeared without any exposure to light. After a time, reddish yellow crystals were precipitated and the solution was left pale yellow. This crystalline precipitate was quite different in appearance from the amorphous precipitate produced by sunlight, a qualitative analysis of which showed the presence of nitrogen, carbon and sulphur. This is probably perthiocyanic acid $\text{C}_2\text{N}_2\text{H}_2\text{S}_2$, which, as is well-known, is produced by action of acids on thiocyanates: $3\text{HCNS} = \text{C}_2\text{N}_2\text{H}_2\text{S}_2 + \text{HCN}$ (Volckel, *Annalen*, 1842, 43, 74; Richter's *Organic Chemistry*).

This action of acids is not characteristic of NH_4CNS only; KCNS also behaves in the same manner.

(iv) The addition of a drop of freshly prepared solution of H_2S discharged the colour of 10 c.c. of a coloured solution of NH_4CNS .

The solution did not regain its colour on exposure to the sun, unless H_2S was boiled off. The action may be represented as follows.

Effects of Air.—Holmes' experiments on exposing a solution of NH_4CNS in an evacuated vessel were repeated and confirmed. Besides that a tube with both the ends closed and having two side tubes provided with stop cocks was completely filled with a 50 per cent. solution of NH_4CNS . On exposure to light, the usual pink colour appeared, but after about an hour the colour began to be discharged until after about two hours, the solution was colourless. A very small amount of precipitate could be seen at the bottom. The experiment was repeated with a boiled out solution, and only a very faint pink colour was developed.

These experiments showed that oxygen was used up in the change, for in the first experiment, the change went on taking place so long as there was any oxygen left.

These conclusions were confirmed by exposing NH_4CNS solution under the atmospheres of gases like H_2 and CO_2 and it was found that no colour change took place.

These experiments rendered it probable that the reaction was due to oxidation. Effect of oxidising agents was, therefore, tried.

(i) *Hydrogen Peroxide.*—The addition of 1 drop of hydrogen peroxide solution to 10 c.c. of 8N solution of NH_4CNS produced a pink colour of exactly the same kind as that produced by sunlight. It behaved in the same manner with respect to dilution, alkalis, H_2S and the action of solvents. On allowing a solution coloured by hydrogen peroxide to stand, a yellow amorphous precipitate of the same description as the one produced by sunlight was obtained.

Other oxidising agents also produced the same colouration. The action of H_2O_2 gave a clue to the probable composition of the precipitate produced by sunlight. It is well known that H_2O_2 , acting on alkali and ammonium thiocyanates produces pseudocyanogen sulphide $(CNS)_2$; therefore the precipitate produced by sunlight was also likely to be $(CNS)_2$. This conclusion is rendered more probable in the light of Ganassini's work (*Boll. Chim. farm.*, 1919, 58, 457). He observed that under the influence of light certain concentrations of potassium thiocyanate were oxidised by air to give pseudocyanogen sulphide according to the equation,

Experiments were tried to find out whether the same gases were given off in the oxidation of NH_4CNS . By bubbling pure air through cold solutions of NH_4CNS (which were exposed to the sun) and then through various reagents, negative results were found for NH_3 and HCN . But by another arrangement, in which a small amount of the reagent in a capillary tube could be brought in contact with the gases produced, many times, the following gases were detected:—

- (i) NH_3 by Nessler's reagent ;
- (ii) SO_2 by KMnO_4 solution which was decoloured and precipitated hydrated manganese dioxide ;
- (iii) HCN by the Schonbein-Pageustacher test (*J. Chem. Ind.*, 1917, 35, 196) which being extremely sensitive has the advantage of detecting HCN in presence of thiocyanates or HCNS .
- (iv) CO_2 and H_2S were not detected,

Electrolysis of NH_4CNS Solution.—A further proof that the colour formation and the precipitate were due to the production of pseudocyanogen sulphide was afforded by the electrolysis of NH_4CNS solutions. Goppelsroeder (*J. Chem. Soc.*, Abs. 1885, 48, 109) found pseudocyanogen sulphide on electrolysis of KCNS solution and in an appendix he acknowledges that A. Lidow found the same substance from NH_4CNS by electrolysis. He gave it the formula $\text{C}_2\text{N}_2\text{HS}_2$, but it is probable that the formula is $\text{C}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$, as the results of analysis to be further described would show.

The experiment was repeated with concentrated solutions with a low current density in the hope that under such conditions the formation of $(\text{CNS})_2$ would be preceded by a red colouration. The conclusion was found to be justified. At the anode a pink colour developed which behaved in the same manner with respect to reagents as the one produced by sunlight and at the cathode ammonia was given off. On passing the current for a longer time, the yellow precipitate of $(\text{CNS})_2$ was obtained. The solution at the anode was acidic, at the cathode alkaline.

CNS' gets discharged and on polymerisation gives $(\text{CNS})_2$, which is precipitated.

Spectroscopic Work.—But the most conclusive proof that the colour produced by sunlight is due to oxidation and is the same as that produced by oxidising the solution with H_2O_2 was afforded by a study of the absorption spectra of solutions of NH_4CNS coloured to the same extent under the action of sunlight and by H_2O_2 .

Work with the Quartz Spectrograph of Adam Hilgers.—A 4.8243 per cent. solution of NH_4CNS was divided into two portions. One was exposed to the sunlight for two days. Both the solutions were then spectrographed. The times of exposure for both the plates were the same; they were developed in developers of the same strength and allowed to remain in the fixing bath for the same time. The length of the column of the liquid through which the light passed could be varied in a Baly's tube with quartz windows at the ends.

In dilute solution the absorption spectra in a column 93 mm. long were identical in the case of the coloured and the non-coloured solutions. The ultra-violet region is completely absorbed in both. No characteristic absorption bands were noticed.

The experiment was next repeated with a more concentrated solution (70.571 grams of NH_4CNS in 100 c.c. of solution) which had been exposed to the sun for four days and it was found that an absorption band appeared in the coloured solution, while in the uncoloured solution there was no such band.

Since the ultra-violet was totally absorbed, it was thought desirable to study the absorption spectra in the visible region by means of Adam Hilger spectrometer of the constant deviation type. The visible region could be extended here and better resolution of lines in that region could be obtained.

The absorption spectra of the following solutions were studied:—

- (a) A freshly prepared solution of NH_4CNS of concentration 70.571 per cent. (Plate No. 2).
- (b) A solution of the same strength exposed to sunlight for 4 days (Plate No. 3).
- (c) A solution of the same strength to which 0.1 c.c. of H_2O_2 was added (Plate No. 4).
- (d) To a solution of 65 g. of NH_4CNS , 6 c.c. of H_2SO_4 diluted to twice their volume were added and the whole made up to 100 c.c. (Plate No. 5)

(e) To a solution of 65 g. of NH_4CNS , 6 c.c. of H_2SO_4 diluted to 12 c.c. were added and the whole made up to 100 c.c.

(f) A 10 per cent. solution of H_2SO_4 in water.

As may be seen from the plates, absorption bands appear only in two cases:—

(1) The solution coloured by sunlight (Plate No. 3).

(2) The solution coloured by H_2O_2 (Plate No. 4) and these bands are exactly of the same type, thus proving that the action is the same in both the cases and that the same substance is produced.

With H_2SO_4 and NH_4CNS no characteristic bands appeared but the absorption spectra differed from the other solutions. That this is not due to the presence of H_2SO_4 is established by the fact that the absorption spectra of H_2SO_4 and water are quite different. This constitutes satisfactory evidence that the action of sunlight is to catalyse the oxidation of NH_4CNS solution by oxygen of the air and thus brings about the same reaction as is brought about by H_2O_2 . It is also clear that although H_2SO_4 brings about a colour change similar, in outward appearance, to the colour change produced by sunlight; the reaction is in reality quite different as indicated by the reaction equation cited in this paper.

Results of Chemical Analysis.—The final evidence in favour of the view put forward is afforded by the results of quantitative analysis.

Elements.	Percentage from the precipitate produced by sunlight (observed).	Percentage from the precipitate by addition of H_2O_2 (observed).	Percentage from (CNS). (calculated).
H	0·7	0·52	0·0
C	20·17	20·43	20·73
N	24·20	24·52	24·14
S	not determined	54·53	55·17

As the quantities of the precipitates obtained were very small, the results shown above may be considered to give a fair indication of the product being pseudocyanogen sulphide with the formula

The Carbon Arc.

53 mm. (length of the column
of solution).

63 mm.

73 mm.

83 mm.

93 mm.

PLATE No. 1.

48-8243% NH₄ONS.

The Carbon Arc.

53 mm. (length of the column
of solution.

63 mm.

73 mm.

83 mm.

93 mm.

PLATE No. 2.

70.571% NH_4ONS (uncoloured).

The Carbon Arc.

58 mm. (length of the column
of solution).

68 mm.

78 mm.

88 mm.

98 mm.

PLATE No. 3.

70-571% NH_4CNS coloured under the action of sunlight.

The Carbon Arc.

53 mm. (length of the column
of solution).

63 mm.

73 mm.

83 mm.

93 mm.

PLATE No. 4.

70.571% $\text{NH}_4\text{CNS} + 0.1$ c.c. of H_2O_2 (to 100 c.c. of solution).

The Carbon Arc.

53 mm. (length of the column
of solution).

63 mm.

73 mm.

83 mm.

93 mm.

PLATE No. 5.

65% NH_4CNS + 6 c.c. H_2SO_4 (to 100 c.c. of solution).

(CNS)₂. The hydrogen indicated in the table probably came from moisture in the extremely small amounts of the precipitate available.

Summary of Results.

The production of colour and precipitate in concentrated solutions of ammonium thiocyanate by sunlight is due to oxidation by the oxygen of air catalysed under the action of sunlight. The principal evidences in favour of this view may be summed up thus:—

1. No colour appears when oxygen is absent, as on exhaustion or when an atmosphere of H₂ or CO₂ is maintained over the solution.
2. The pink colour and the precipitate produced are exactly of the same kind and behave in the same manner as the colour and precipitate produced by the addition of even a single drop of H₂O₂ to so much as 70 grams of NH₄CNS.
3. The absorption spectra of the coloured solution (by sunlight) and the one coloured by H₂O₂ are exactly of the same kind.
4. Analysis shows that the C and H content of both the precipitates is the same.

Possible Mechanism of the Reaction.—In view of the facts enumerated above it is probable that by oxidation of ammonium thiocyanate pseudocyanogen sulphide is produced, and since the change only takes place in presence of free HCNS, it is but reasonable to assume that NH₄CNS is hydrolysed by water to HCNS and NH₄OH; and that HCNS is oxidised by oxygen to give CNS which is responsible for the colour.

This CNS further polymerises to give (CNS)₂, which is precipitated as pseudocyanogen sulphide.

The last two reactions are irreversible although at first the fact that in darkness the colour disappears, suggests that the action is reversible. But the experiment above described of exposing a solution which contains dissolved air only to sunlight when the red coloured produced at first disappears giving a small precipitate shows that the action is irreversible.

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